

ABRomics-DB

Progress of the β version release

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ABRomics-DB

Strain of a biological sample is associated to:

- A group of users
- Metadata
- Sequencing information
- ABRomics bioinformatics results ...
- ... including ABR prediction

Stored and structured with a relational database

Overview of the ABRomics DB structure

